

Vessel passage scheduling through cascaded bridges using mixed-integer programming^{*}

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Abstract: This paper addresses the problem of guaranteeing efficient inland waterway transport in the presence of sequential movable bridges, which must be operated to grant vessel passage. The main contribution is the formulation of the vessel passage scheduling problem as a mixed-integer programming problem. The scheduling algorithm receives vessel widths and voyage plans, and determines feasible vessel passage through bridges that best matches vessel plans. Process optimization is carried out using a rolling horizon implementation to keep the problem computationally tractable in real-time applications. Finally, a realistic case study based on the Rhine-Alpine corridor is used to test the approach and demonstrate its effectiveness.

Keywords: Real-time transportation operations, intelligent transportation systems, scheduling.

1. INTRODUCTION

Inland waterways are large-scale systems consisting of artificial canals and natural rivers, and are mainly used for freight transportation (Segovia et al., 2019). Inland waterway transport (IWT) is one of the most cost-effective and environmentally friendly transport modes to move large amounts of cargo (Ji et al., 2019b), two features that account for its widespread utilization. For instance, the Rhine-Alpine corridor, which connects the North Sea to the Mediterranean basin, handles an annual throughput of more than a billion tonnes of freight (European Commission and Innovation and Networks Executive Agency, 2018). The Three Gorges Dam (Yangtze river, China) also processed over a billion tonnes in 2018 (Zhao et al., 2019).

IWT is a complex system that involves many interacting systems, most notably vessels and infrastructure. This fact constitutes one of the main differences with respect to overseas transport. Moreover, water level variability in inland waterways poses additional challenges for vessels in terms of navigability and interaction with infrastructure. As a consequence of this complexity, inland shipping has experienced a gradual change of paradigm, from decision making based on human experience to embracing the modern trend of big data era (Yan et al., 2018). On the other hand, recent advancements in communication technologies and computational intelligence have facilitated the advent of *smart* vessels (Du et al., 2021), which can process real-time information and optimize their voyage plans. Therefore, increased levels of digitalization and automation are expected for IWT in the near future (Ye et al., 2021).

The inherent complexity of modern IWT requires the adoption and application of appropriate strategies to guarantee an adequate system coordination. In the absence of coordination, navigation delays may arise. Returning to the example of cargo transport along the Yangtze river, Zhao et al. (2019) report that more than two hundred vessels can accumulate at the Three Gorges Dam anchorage during peak time, with an average time to pass the dam of thirty hours. It can be concluded that there is room for operational performance improvement.

One possibility consists in formulating management problems in an optimization framework, as their resolution yields decisions that maximize a profit function while respecting constraints. There is a large body of literature on optimization-based IWT management. Golias et al. (2014) tackle the discrete berth scheduling problem with uncertain vessel arrival and handling times, determining robust schedules that minimize average and range of service times. Lalla-Ruiz et al. (2018) build a mathematical model to assign waterways to incoming and outgoing port vessels to minimize waiting times. Hill et al. (2018) reformulate the previous problem to incorporate time-dependent resource capacities, and solve it using integer programming. Chen et al. (2020) schedule passage of vessel train formations through cascaded waterborne intersections.

One of the main bottlenecks in IWT arises from the interaction between vessels and infrastructure, e.g., locks and bridges, which interrupt navigation frequently. Therefore, optimal vessel passage scheduling through infrastructure has received considerable attention. Verstichel et al. (2014) propose an integrated approach to the lock scheduling problem, comprising ship placement, chamber assignment and lockage scheduling. Passchyn et al. (2016) tackle the scheduling of a series of consecutive locks with single chambers while paying attention to the trade-off between sailing time and emissions. Ji et al. (2019a) also study the co-scheduling of cascaded locks, but address the multiple

^{*} This research is supported by the project “Novel inland waterway transport concepts for moving freight effectively (NOVIMOVE)”. This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 858508.

chamber case. Ji et al. (2021) approach the cascaded lock scheduling problem as well, but their approach has its roots in job shop scheduling and multi-commodity flow.

Although lock operation is a complicated process and can impact vessel navigation, it does not affect other traffic systems. Road and rail traffic make use of available bridges to connect two portions of land that are separated by water flows. Naturally, the operation of movable bridges to enable vessel passage disrupts other traffic, especially given the current state of practice, which prioritizes vessel passage over seamless road and rail traffic (Rijkswaterstaat, Center for Water, Transport and Environment (WVL), 2020). Main operational principles dictate that bridge operators try to fulfill passage requests from vessels as soon as possible, which is granted after making sure that there is no congestion on the bridge deck. Therefore, waterborne, road and rail transport are closely intertwined as a result of bridge operations. Increased infrastructure operation is desirable from the standpoint of IWT, but deteriorates the performance of the other transport modes, aside from resulting in increased wear and tear of infrastructure. On the contrary, limited bridge opening regimes are likely to result in increased waiting times for vessels.

Improved operational performance can be achieved by introducing vessel-to-infrastructure (V2I) communication, which allows vessels to share their voyage plans with bridges in advance. In turn, bridges can process information from multiple vessels, anticipate demand and assign modified arrival times that are best aligned with vessel voyage plans. This approach can be used to tackle vessel passage scheduling through cascaded bridges, whereby vessels are scheduled through a sequence of movable bridges to reach the final destination before the deadline.

The main contribution of this paper is the formulation of the vessel passage scheduling problem as a mixed-integer programming problem. The optimization criterion consists in minimizing deviations between vessel voyage plans and assigned passing times through bridges by the scheduler, and is formulated as a sum of convex piecewise-linear functions. Moreover, a rolling horizon implementation is proposed to render the approach amenable to real-time implementations.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: the vessel passage scheduling problem is described in Section 2. Section 3 presents a scheduling approach based on mixed-integer programming. A realistic case study based on the Rhine-Alpine corridor is described and tested in Section 4, which allows to draw conclusions and outline future research in Section 5.

2. PROBLEM STATEMENT

The vessel passage scheduling problem through cascaded bridges can be formulated as follows. A set of vessels $\mathcal{V} = \{1, \dots, N_v\}$ must pass a set of movable bridges $\mathcal{B} = \{1, \dots, N_b\}$ on their way from origin to destination. Moreover, $\mathcal{V} = \mathcal{V}_d \cup \mathcal{V}_u$, where \mathcal{V}_d and \mathcal{V}_u denote vessels traveling downstream (from inland towards the sea) and upstream (from the sea towards inland), respectively, and $\mathcal{V}_u \cap \mathcal{V}_d = \emptyset$. A discrete problem setting is adopted, and thus time is divided into a set of time steps $\mathcal{K} = \{1, \dots, N\}$ of equal

length. Vessel i is characterized by its width w_i [m] and its voyage plans, i.e., earliest and optimal arrival instants at bridge j , $\tau_{ij}^e, \tau_{ij}^o \in \mathbb{Z}_+$, respectively, $\forall i \in \mathcal{V}, \forall j \in \mathcal{B}$, with \mathbb{Z}_+ the set of positive integers. These arrival instants can be determined considering the maximum speed and the speed that minimizes fuel consumption, respectively. On the other hand, bridge j is described by its passage width b_j [m] and a schedule $s_j \in \mathbb{Z}_+^{n_j}$, i.e., a vector of n_j opening instants, $\forall j \in \mathcal{B}$. Fixed bridge timetables are assumed, and are provided as input data to the scheduling problem.

The assumptions of the problem are listed below:

- Clearance under bridges (measured from water surface to bridge underside) is not sufficient for vessels to sail below bridges while these are closed.
- Choice of time step size is sufficiently large for vessel i to pass bridge j in one time step with zero dwell time, $\forall i \in \mathcal{V}, \forall j \in \mathcal{B}$.
- Choice of time step size also allows to consider that bridge is either open or closed.
- There are no safety periods between consecutive vessels—bridge opening schedule s_j already accounts for this feature, $\forall j \in \mathcal{B}$.

Then, the decision variables used in the mathematical problem formulation are as follows:

- $T_{ij} \in \mathbb{Z}_+$ denotes the integer time instant at which vessel i is scheduled to pass bridge j , $\forall i \in \mathcal{V}, \forall j \in \mathcal{B}$.
- $\delta_{ijk} = \{0, 1\}$ is a binary variable that equals 1 if vessel i passes bridge j at time instant k , $\forall i \in \mathcal{V}, \forall j \in \mathcal{B}, \forall k \in \mathcal{K}$, and 0 otherwise.

The objective of the vessel passage scheduling problem is to determine T_{ij}, δ_{ijk} in such a way that the optimal passing times provided by vessels are satisfied by the solution of the scheduling algorithm as much as possible. The design of the problem is tackled in the next section.

3. PROPOSED APPROACH

The vessel passage scheduling problem can be modeled using ideas from the job shop scheduling problem. Broadly speaking, jobs (vessel passage) must be assigned to machines (bridges) so as to optimize a certain performance criterion (Ku and Beck, 2016).

A centralized decision entity—the *scheduler*—receives $\tau_{ij}^e, \tau_{ij}^o, w_i$, and determines suitable T_{ij}, δ_{ijk} , $\forall i \in \mathcal{V}, \forall j \in \mathcal{B}, \forall k \in \mathcal{K}$. It is assumed that all vessels adhere to the solution determined by the scheduler using local vessel controllers, which ensure that the arrival times of vessels at bridges fulfill the scheduler solution. The design of local vessel controllers is out of the scope of the paper.

The performance criterion is formulated first. Then, physical and operational constraints are defined. Finally, a rolling horizon implementation is considered to account for real-time provision of information.

3.1 Cost function design

The main operational goal consists in minimizing the *scheduling error*, i.e., the mismatch between τ_{ij}^o and T_{ij} , $\forall i \in \mathcal{V}, \forall j \in \mathcal{B}$. A cost function J defined as the sum of

$N_v \cdot N_b$ convex piecewise-linear functions—one per vessel and bridge—is employed in this paper. This cost function description is well suited to describe real-life conditions, e.g., unequal penalties on earliness and tardiness.

Cost function J is defined as $J \triangleq \sum_{i \in \mathcal{V}} \sum_{j \in \mathcal{B}} J_{ij}(T_{ij})$, where $J_{ij}(T_{ij})$ quantifies the penalty corresponding to vessel i passing bridge j , and is formulated as

$$J_{ij}(T_{ij}) = \begin{cases} a_{ij}^{(1)} T_{ij} + b_{ij}^{(1)} & \text{if } T_{ij} \in [l_{ij}^{(1)}, u_{ij}^{(1)}], \\ a_{ij}^{(2)} T_{ij} + b_{ij}^{(2)} & \text{if } T_{ij} \in (u_{ij}^{(1)}, u_{ij}^{(2)}], \\ \vdots & \\ a_{ij}^{(n_{ij})} T_{ij} + b_{ij}^{(n_{ij})} & \text{if } T_{ij} \in (u_{ij}^{(n_{ij}-1)}, u_{ij}^{(n_{ij})}], \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where $a_{ij}^{(m)}$ and $b_{ij}^{(m)}$ characterize interval m . Moreover, $l_{ij}^{(1)}$ and $u_{ij}^{(m)}$ are the lower and upper bounds of intervals 1 and m , respectively, $\forall m \in \{1, \dots, n_{ij}\}$, and n_{ij} is the total number of intervals into which J_{ij} is divided.

The large degree of parametrization can be used to reflect multiple real-life features:

- Larger mismatches between T_{ij} and τ_{ij}^o should be increasingly penalized. Then, the farther the interval from τ_{ij}^o , the steeper the sub-function slope should be.
- Furthermore, if the exact optimal times of arrival cannot be satisfied, scheduling policies favor vessel earliness over tardiness—although both incur costs.
- While all vessels should be equally treated for the sake of fairness, wide vessels take up more bridge width than narrow vessels. Thus, wider vessels should incur larger scheduling error penalties.
- Scheduling error may also be tailored to each bridge based on, e.g., road and/or rail traffic condition on its deck and safety concerns.

These ideas are illustrated by means of Figure 1. Convex piecewise-linear functions are depicted for two vessels of different width with the same optimal arrival times at the same bridge, hence the subscripts i and j have been dropped. Moreover, Δ_1 and Δ_2 are parameters introduced to denote the interval sizes in (1), and have been chosen as vessel- and bridge-independent in this case.

Then, the following reformulation of (1) is proposed based on the ideas introduced in Figure 1:

$$J_{ij}(T_{ij}) = \begin{cases} \infty & \text{if } T_{ij} \leq \tau_{ij}^o - \Delta_{ij,2}, \\ a_{ij}^{(1)} T_{ij} + b_{ij}^{(1)} & \text{if } \tau_{ij}^o - \Delta_{ij,2} < T_{ij} \leq \tau_{ij}^o - \Delta_{ij,1}, \\ a_{ij}^{(2)} T_{ij} + b_{ij}^{(2)} & \text{if } \tau_{ij}^o - \Delta_{ij,1} < T_{ij} \leq \tau_{ij}^o, \\ a_{ij}^{(3)} T_{ij} + b_{ij}^{(3)} & \text{if } \tau_{ij}^o < T_{ij} \leq \tau_{ij}^o + \Delta_{ij,1}, \\ a_{ij}^{(4)} T_{ij} + b_{ij}^{(4)} & \text{if } \tau_{ij}^o + \Delta_{ij,1} < T_{ij} \leq \tau_{ij}^o + \Delta_{ij,2}, \\ \infty & \text{if } T_{ij} \geq \tau_{ij}^o + \Delta_{ij,2}, \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

and $a_{ij}^{(m)}$ and $b_{ij}^{(m)}$ can be computed using desired slope values and $\Delta_{ij,1}, \Delta_{ij,2}, \forall i \in \mathcal{V}, \forall j \in \mathcal{B}$, and $m = 1, 2, 3, 4$. Numerical values may be chosen based on costs associated to vessel earliness and tardiness, e.g., mooring costs.

Fig. 1. Piecewise-linear functions for vessels 1 (gray solid) and 2 (black dashed) classes, with $w_1 < w_2$. Vertical black dotted and red solid lines delimit intervals and admissible scheduling interval, respectively.

3.2 Formulation of operational constraints

The set of restrictions that must be satisfied during system operation are as follows:

- Vessel passage cannot be scheduled before earliest times of arrival at bridges:

$$T_{ij} \geq \tau_{ij}^e, \forall i \in \mathcal{V}, \forall j \in \mathcal{B}. \quad (3)$$

- Vessel passage can only take place if bridges are open:

$$T_{ij} \in s_j, \forall i \in \mathcal{V}, \forall j \in \mathcal{B}. \quad (4)$$

- Vessels pass each bridge exactly once:

$$\sum_{k \in \mathcal{K}} \delta_{ijk} = 1, \forall i \in \mathcal{V}, \forall j \in \mathcal{B}. \quad (5)$$

- Multiple vessels may pass the bridge simultaneously as long as their combined widths (plus appropriate safety distances) do not exceed bridge passage width:

$$\sum_{i \in \mathcal{V}} w_i \delta_{ijk} \leq b_j, \forall j \in \mathcal{B}, \forall k \in \mathcal{K}. \quad (6)$$

Note that safety distances may be incorporated to vessel widths $w_i, \forall i \in \mathcal{V}$.

- Vessels must pass all bridges in the correct order:

$$T_{i(j+1)} \geq T_{ij}, \forall i \in \mathcal{V}_d, \forall j \in \mathcal{B} \setminus \{N_b\}, \quad (7a)$$

$$T_{i(j+1)} \leq T_{ij}, \forall i \in \mathcal{V}_u, \forall j \in \mathcal{B} \setminus \{N_b\}. \quad (7b)$$

It is assumed that bridges are numbered in such a way that the first and last bridges are at the upstream and downstream ends of the system, respectively.

- Passing times of vessels are bounded:

$$T_{ij} \leq N, \forall i \in \mathcal{V}, \forall j \in \mathcal{B}. \quad (8)$$

- Decision variables T_{ij} and δ_{ijk} are linked as follows: ($\delta_{ijk} = 1$) \rightarrow ($T_{ij} = k$). This can be re-written as

$$\left. \begin{aligned} T_{ij} - k &\leq (1 - \delta_{ijk}) M \\ k - T_{ij} &\leq (1 - \delta_{ijk}) M \end{aligned} \right\} \forall i \in \mathcal{V}, \forall j \in \mathcal{B}, \forall k \in \mathcal{K}, \quad (9)$$

where M is a scalar that must be large enough to ensure correctness of (9). Following the reasoning of Ku and Beck (2016), $M \triangleq N_v \cdot N_b \cdot N$ is a suitable constant, as it is infeasible that all vessels are scheduled to pass all bridges at the last time instant.

3.3 Vessel scheduling: a rolling horizon implementation

The vessel passage scheduling problem through cascaded bridges can be formulated as follows:

$$\min_{T_{ij}, \delta_{ijk}} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{V}} \sum_{j \in \mathcal{B}} J_{ij}(T_{ij}) \quad (10a)$$

subject to:

$$\text{Constraints (3)–(9),} \quad (10b)$$

$$T_{ij} \in \mathbb{Z}_+, \delta_{ijk} = \{0, 1\}, \forall i \in \mathcal{V}, \forall j \in \mathcal{B}, \forall k \in \mathcal{K}. \quad (10c)$$

Problem (10) can be recast in the mixed-integer programming framework by introducing auxiliary binary and real variables (Bemporad and Morari, 1999). The interested reader is referred to the work of Ferrari-Trecate et al. (2001), which reports the necessary steps in detail. The main steps are summarized below for convenience:

- $n_{ij} - 1$ binary variables $\epsilon_{ij}^{(l)} = \{0, 1\}$ must be introduced for J_{ij} , $\forall i \in \mathcal{V}, \forall j \in \mathcal{B}, l = 1, \dots, n_{ij} - 1$. Then, $\epsilon_{ij}^{(l)}$ equals 1 if $T_{ij} > u_{ij}^{(l)}$ following the notation in (1), and 0 otherwise.
- $n_{ij} - 1$ variables $z_{ij}^{(l)} \in \mathbb{R}$ must be introduced for J_{ij} . Define \tilde{z}_{ij} as $\tilde{z}_{ij} \triangleq \sum_{l=1}^{n_{ij}-1} z_{ij}^{(l)}$. Each combination of values of $\epsilon_{ij}^{(l)}$ activates a single $z_{ij}^{(l)}$, $l = 1, \dots, n_{ij} - 1$, thus selecting a different interval of J_{ij} .
- Additional constraints must be defined to connect the original decision variables T_{ij}, δ_{ijk} with the auxiliary variables $\epsilon_{ij}^{(l)}, z_{ij}^{(l)}, \tilde{z}_{ij}$ to reformulate (10) as a mixed-integer programming problem.
- These manipulations allow to transform (10) into the following mixed-integer program:

$$\min_{T_{ij}, \delta_{ijk}, \epsilon_{ij}^{(l)}, z_{ij}^{(l)}, \tilde{z}_{ij}} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{V}} \sum_{j \in \mathcal{B}} \tilde{z}_{ij} \quad (11a)$$

subject to:

$$\text{Constraints (3)–(9),} \quad (11b)$$

$$\text{Additional constraints connecting } T_{ij}, \delta_{ijk}, \quad (11c)$$

$$\epsilon_{ij}^{(l)}, z_{ij}^{(l)}, \forall i \in \mathcal{V}, \forall j \in \mathcal{B}, \forall k \in \mathcal{K}, l = 1, \dots, n_{ij} - 1,$$

$$T_{ij} \in \mathbb{Z}_+, \delta_{ijk} = \{0, 1\}, \epsilon_{ij}^{(l)} = \{0, 1\}, z_{ij}^{(l)} \in \mathbb{R}, \quad (11d)$$

$$\forall i \in \mathcal{V}, \forall j \in \mathcal{B}, \forall k \in \mathcal{K}, l = 1, \dots, n_{ij} - 1.$$

Both (10) and (11) are characterized by a combinatorial nature due to the existence of binary- and discrete-valued variables. These problems scale poorly, as the necessary effort to determine optimal solutions increases drastically for increased problem sizes (Bragin et al., 2019). In this particular application, the need to schedule the passage of new vessels through the bridges as time progresses may render the problem computationally intractable.

The rolling horizon framework appears to be well suited to tackle the problem at hand, as it uses a sliding time window that is shifted in time to solve smaller subproblems that are bounded in size (Zhan et al., 2010). The benefits of formulating the vessel passage scheduling problem in this framework are twofold. On the one hand, computational complexity issues can be kept at bay. On the other hand, real-time information can be processed as time progresses. Nevertheless, and while optimal decisions are obtained for each subproblem, the solution of the overall problem might be suboptimal, as the subproblems solved at each time

Algorithm 1 Vessel passage scheduling through cascaded bridges using a rolling horizon implementation

Require: at time instant k , (i) all data for vessels with $\tau_{ij}^e = k, \forall i \in \mathcal{V}, \forall j \in \mathcal{B}$, and (ii) bridge schedule s_j and available bridge width $b_{jk}, \forall j \in \mathcal{B}, \forall k \in \mathcal{K}$

- 1: Initialization: $b_{jk} \leftarrow b_j, \forall j \in \mathcal{B}, \forall k \in \mathcal{K}$
- 2: **for** $k = 1 : N$ **do**
- 3: **if** $\tau_{ij}^e = k, \forall i \in \mathcal{V}, \forall j \in \mathcal{B}$ **then**
- 4: Solve (11) for vessels s.t. $\tau_{ij}^e = k, \forall i \in \mathcal{V}, \forall j \in \mathcal{B}$
- 5: $b_{jk} \leftarrow b_{jk} - \sum_{i \in \mathcal{V}} w_i \delta_{ijk}, \forall j \in \mathcal{B}, \forall k \in \mathcal{K}$
- 6: **else**
- 7: **end if**
- 8: **end for**

step do not make use of future information (Silvente et al., 2015). Be that as it may, the practical advantages that a rolling horizon implementation offers for the vessel passage scheduling problem outweigh the drawbacks.

Algorithm 1 sketches the necessary steps to solve the vessel passage scheduling problem using a rolling horizon implementation. Subproblem resolution at time instant k yields the scheduling of vessels with $\tau_{ij}^e = k, \forall i \in \mathcal{V}, \forall j \in \mathcal{B}, \forall k \in \mathcal{K}$. Furthermore, b_{jk} , which denotes the available width of bridge j at time instant k , is initialized at passage width $b_j, \forall j \in \mathcal{B}, \forall k \in \mathcal{K}$. Then, available bridge widths are updated at each time instant after the corresponding solution has been obtained, thus connecting consecutive subproblems.

4. CASE STUDY

4.1 System description

The Rhine-Alpine corridor connects major economic centers such as Brussels and Antwerp (Belgium), the Randstad region (the Netherlands), the Rhine-Ruhr and Rhine-Neckar regions (Germany), and the regions of Milan and Genoa (Italy). This corridor constitutes one of the busiest European freight routes, as it connects the ports of Rotterdam and Antwerp to the Mediterranean basin, with a throughput that represents 19% of EU's total GDP (European Commission and Innovation and Networks Executive Agency, 2018).

The Beneden Merwede is identified as a suitable case study within the Rhine-Alpine corridor, and consists in a stretch of river in the Netherlands that runs between Dordrecht and Hardinxveld-Giessendam. A schematic representation is provided in Figure 2, which has been obtained using a tool developed by Rijkswaterstaat¹. Road and railway movable bridges can be found in that stretch, whose data are provided in Table 1. It can be observed that the first and second bridges are very close to one another. Moreover, bridge schedules are assumed to be fixed and equal for all bridges in this work.

4.2 Experimental design

A fleet of vessels is considered to sail from Dordrecht to Hardinxveld-Giessendam, which requires to pass the movable bridges introduced in Table 1. The following guidelines are observed to generate an appropriate fleet:

¹ <https://vaarweginformatie.nl/>

Table 1. Movable bridges in the Beneden Merwede

Bridge	Width [m]	Assumed fixed schedule	Approx. distance from previous bridge [m]
(1) Traffic bridge Dordrecht	44	6:50-7:00, 7:50-8:00, 8:50-9:00, 9:50-10:00,	—
(2) Railway bridge Grotebrug	44	10:50-11:00, 11:50-12:00, 12:50-13:00,	50
(3) Traffic bridge Papendrecht	30	13:50-14:00, 14:50-15:00, 15:50-16:00, 16:50-17:00,	4500
(4) Railway bridge Baanhoek	30	17:50-18:00, 18:50-19:00, 19:50-20:00	2500

Fig. 2. Schematic representation of the Beneden Merwede

- All vessel widths must be smaller than the narrowest bridge. Widths must then be selected such that $w_i < \min(b_j)$, safety distances included, $\forall i \in \mathcal{V}, \forall j \in \mathcal{B}$.
- The vessel passage scheduling problem is solved for one day. Moreover, bridge opening regimes start at 6 a.m. and finish at 8 p.m., in accordance with Table 1.
- In order for the scheduling problem to be feasible, values for τ_{ij}^e, τ_{ij}^o that enable vessels to be scheduled in the same day must be considered, $\forall i \in \mathcal{V}, \forall j \in \mathcal{B}$.

A cost function (2) is defined for vessel i and bridge j , $\forall i \in \mathcal{V}, \forall j \in \mathcal{B}$. As discussed in Section 3.1, the parameters are selected in such way that larger penalties are set for wider vessels. On the one hand, numerical values of $a_{ij}^{(l)}$ and $b_{ij}^{(l)}$ are selected as follows:

- The following values of $a_{ij}^{(l)}$ are selected for the smallest vessel in the fleet: $a_{ij}^{(2)} = 15^\circ$, $a_{ij}^{(3)} = a_{ij}^{(4)} = 10^\circ$ and $a_{ij}^{(5)} = 20^\circ$, where \hat{i} indicates the smallest vessel. These values are increased per additional meter of width for the rest of vessels: $a_{ij}^{(2)} = a_{ij}^{(2)} + 3^\circ/\text{m}$, $a_{ij}^{(3)} = a_{ij}^{(4)} = a_{ij}^{(3)} + 2^\circ/\text{m}$ and $a_{ij}^{(5)} = a_{ij}^{(5)} + 4^\circ/\text{m}$.
- The values of $b_{ij}^{(l)}$ can be computed using the values chosen for $a_{ij}^{(l)}$ and $\Delta_{ij,1}, \Delta_{ij,2}$. Dependency of the latter on vessel and bridge is dropped, and the values $\Delta_1 = 2$ hours and $\Delta_2 = 5$ hours are selected.

4.3 Results

Based on the above guidelines, a fleet of vessels is generated, and their passing times through the four movable bridges are scheduled using Algorithm 1. Simulations are performed in a computer with an Intel Core i7-8665U processor running at 1.9GHz with 8GB RAM. Results are obtained in Matlab R2020b using Gurobi Optimization 9.1.2² and the YALMIP toolbox (Löfberg, 2004).

A time step size of five minutes is selected, which imposes an upper bound on the runtime of Algorithm 1. Its selection is deemed appropriate from the standpoint of system

operation. Although discrete times are denoted with integers, these values are translated into corresponding five-minute time intervals for the sake of clarity.

Before proceeding with the analysis of the results, it must be noted that the first and second bridges are treated as a single bridge in practice, and thus scheduling results are identical for both bridges. This assumption is deemed reasonable considering the inter-bridge distance, which is of only fifty meters as reported in Table 1. Then, results for the first and second bridges are identical, and are thus provided in the same plots.

Comparison of optimal vessel voyage plans, i.e., τ_{ij}^o , and assigned arrival times determined by the scheduler, i.e., T_{ij} , is provided in Figures 3, 4 and 5 for the first-second, third and fourth bridges, respectively. In the absence of a scheduling mechanism, vessels arrive at bridges at their optimal arrival times (depicted in red), which are outside the schedules for the most part. Conversely, the scheduler assigns arrival times (depicted in blue) within bridge opening schedules, thus fulfilling constraint (4). Note that the overlaps that occur when the scheduler can assign passing times T_{ij} (blue) that match optimal voyage plans τ_{ij}^o (red) can be identified in Figures 3–5 by single blue lines for a given vessel.

It must be noted that Figures 3–5 do not provide complete vessel voyage plans, as earliest arrival times are not depicted to avoid cluttered figures. Therefore, while it might appear as if bridges still admit more vessels to pass simultaneously, earliest arrivals might take place later than the closest bridge opening slot. An example of this is vessel 5 in Figure 5, whose optimal arrival time is closer to the 9:50–10:00 slot, but is actually assigned to pass at 10:50. In these cases, the scheduler assigns values of T_{ij} that belong to a future opening slot (with respect to τ_{ij}^e and τ_{ij}^o) to ensure satisfaction of constraint (3).

It was discussed in Section 3.3 that overall problem resolution using a rolling horizon implementation might not yield optimal schedules. This can be realized by considering vessels 47 and 53 in Figure 4. While the optimal arrival time of vessel 47 is five minutes earlier than that of vessel 53, the latter is scheduled to pass before the former. This is due to the fact that schedules are built in an incremental manner, and the rolling horizon scheduling strategy operates through provision of earliest arrival times. In this particular case, the earliest arrival time of vessel 53 is smaller than that of vessel 47, which is why it is scheduled to pass before. However, a rolling horizon implementation allows for real-time scheduling, even more considering the upper bound on runtime equal to five minutes.

Bridge width occupancy considering the scheduler solution is provided in Figures 6, 7 and 8 for the first-second, third and fourth bridges, respectively. In this case, green bars represent the maximum passage width b_j during opening

² <https://www.gurobi.com/products/gurobi-optimizer/>

Fig. 3. Comparison of optimal voyage plans τ_{ij}^o (red) and scheduler solution T_{ij} (blue) at first and second bridges. Overlaps between τ_{ij}^o and T_{ij} result in single blue lines for the corresponding vessels

Fig. 4. Comparison of optimal voyage plans τ_{ij}^o (red) and scheduler solution T_{ij} (blue) at third bridge. Overlaps between τ_{ij}^o and T_{ij} result in single blue lines for the corresponding vessels

Fig. 5. Comparison of optimal voyage plans τ_{ij}^o (red) and scheduler solution T_{ij} (blue) at fourth bridge. Overlaps between τ_{ij}^o and T_{ij} result in single blue lines for the corresponding vessels

time windows, while blue bars indicate total resource (bridge width) usage by vessels. It can be seen that the scheduler succeeds in assigning feasible passing times from the standpoint of resource availability, thus fulfilling constraint (6). Moreover, smaller width of third and fourth bridges (with respect to first and second bridges) accounts for the fact that the former are characterized by a larger resource usage.

Fig. 6. Width occupancy of first and second bridges

Fig. 7. Width occupancy of third bridge

Fig. 8. Width occupancy of fourth bridge

5. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE RESEARCH

This paper presented a formulation of the vessel passage scheduling problem through cascaded bridges using mixed-integer programming. Vessel passage must be scheduled so as to minimize the mismatch between optimal vessel voyage plans and feasible passage determined by the scheduling algorithm. To this end, vessel dimensions, and earliest and optimal arrival times at bridges are provided as inputs to the scheduling algorithm, which processes them and sends an accepted or a modified arrival time back to each individual vessel. The optimality criterion was formulated as a sum of convex piecewise-linear functions.

Analysis of the results suggested that the scheduler is constrained by a given combination of arrival times and bridge schedules. Extension to the case of optimized bridge opening regimes will be examined, thus adapting bridge

operation to the current navigation demand. Future work also regards the design of local vessel controllers that guarantee arrival times at bridges in compliance with the solution determined by the scheduler.

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